

Security Trade-offs in Memristive In-Memory Computing

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Abstract

Memristors as a fourth fundamental circuit element has emerged as a promising solution for energy efficient neural network interface and hardware cryptography which exploits variability, non-volatility, analog granularity, and crossbar density of memristive devices. These same physical properties introduce an underexplored attack surface that is different from the conventional CMOS-based systems. This paper presents a structured literature review of security trade-offs in memristive in-memory computing architectures. We review the usage of memristors in Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) and True Random Number Generators (TRNGs), analog encryption schemes, and logic-in-memory (LIM) cryptographic circuits. We further analyze the vulnerability studies including side-channel attacks on MAGIC-based LIM, fault injection (FI) attacks, power-based reverse engineering attacks on spiking neural networks and model theft in NN accelerators architecture such as PRIME. We also discuss the trade-offs of countermeasures such as power-balanced hiding, weight transformation, model encryption, and fingerprint embedding. There are 2 key findings across the reviewed works: (i) the absence of a unified defence framework capable of addressing side channel leakage, fault injection, white-box extraction, and learning attacks without incurring prohibitive hardware, energy, or endurance overheads; (ii) an identified open research challenge regarding the lack of fabricated hardware validation for the countermeasures proposed.

Keywords—memristor; in-memory computing; side-channel attack; hardware security; ReRAM; logic-in-memory; neural network security; PUF; TRNG; cryptographic hardware

1. Introduction

Memristor device was first postulated by Chua in 1971 as the 4th fundamental passive circuit element which he defined by the relation between charge and flux [1]. The memristive relationship is expressed as:

$$M(q) = \frac{d\varphi}{dq} \quad (1)$$

where $M(q)$ is the memristance, φ is the magnetic flux, and q is the electric charge. This quantity governs the instantaneous voltage–current relationship:

$$v(t) = M(q(t)) \cdot i(t) \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) expresses the property of a memristor: the effective resistance $M(q(t))$ of a memristor depends on the history of current flows through the device over time, unlike a resistor whose resistance is linear and does not depend on the history of the current passed through. Practical implementations later emerged through Resistive Random Access Memory (ReRAM) technology in physical realizations of memristors using transition metal oxide thin films [2, 3]. Due to their non-volatility, analog computation capability, and high density crossbar structures, memristors have gained significant attention in key applications like neural network accelerators, cryptographic logic circuits, keyless encryption engines, PUFs (Physically Unclonable Functions) and TRNGs (True Random Number Generators) [6]. These cryptographic domain applications open up a new attack surface on the implementation of these algorithms. The attractive features (non-volatility, analog granularity, crossbar density) of memristors also define a distinctive and unexplored attack surface. In this literature review, we discuss the possible attack surfaces and the work done so far to address these attack surfaces.

2. Background on Memristive Computing & Security

2.1 Device Physics & Architecture

Memristors are divided into two major classes based on the mobile ionic species involved in resistive switching:

- **Anion based:** Oxygen vacancies act as the mobile species. These devices are commonly referred to as Valence Change Memory (VCM) devices.
- **Cation based:** Metal ions such as Cu or Ag ions form or dissolve conductive filaments in the switching layer. These devices are commonly known as Electrochemical Metalization (ECM) or Conductive Bridging Random Access Memory (CBRAM) devices and have greater dependency on electric field and temperature.

Switching dynamics of a memristor is governed by the non-linear ionic transport and depends on electric field and temperature. This dependency leads to a trade-off of faster switching and shorter retention. Typical endurance of modern devices ranges from 10^{10} cycles in Hf-O systems to 10^{12} cycles in TaOx based devices [2, 3].

The two resistive states—Low Resistance State (LRS) and High Resistance State (HRS)

give rise to different currents under an applied voltage V :

$$I_{\text{LRS}} = \frac{V}{R_{\text{on}}} \quad (\text{order of mA}), \quad I_{\text{HRS}} = \frac{V}{R_{\text{off}}} \quad (\text{order of } \mu\text{A}) \quad (3)$$

the leakage ratio tells us how much the power consumption differs between two states, this is an important parameter as it affects both how reliably the memory works and how vulnerable it is to power-analysis attacks.

$$\frac{I_{\text{LRS}}}{I_{\text{HRS}}} = \frac{R_{\text{off}}}{R_{\text{on}}} \quad (4)$$

values of $R_{\text{off}}/R_{\text{on}}$ are often several orders of magnitude, which means any adversary taping the power consumption passively can distinguish LRS from HRS, a property of the side-channel vulnerabilities discussed in Section 5.

At the architectural level, memristors are commonly organised in crossbar arrays where devices sit at the intersection of wordlines and bitlines, enabling highly efficient analog vector–matrix multiplication (VMM). The current accumulated at the j -th bitline during a VMM operation is:

$$i_j = \sum_{i=1}^m v_i \cdot c_{i,j} \quad (5)$$

where v_i is the input voltage applied to the i -th wordline and $c_{i,j}$ is the conductance (stored weight) of the memristor at row i , column j . A newly introduced architecture proposed by chi et al. [5] PRIME architecture based Processing in Memory (PIM) shows a significant improvement in computational performance and energy efficiency.

2.2 Security Context

The non-volatile nature of memristor devices has significant advantages in terms of computation and energy efficiency; at the same time it also introduces important security concerns. Storing neural-network weights on the device increases the risk of information leakage via side-channel attacks by exploiting memory access patterns and—more aggressively—by micro-probing the device. Zou et al. [6] formalised two basic threat models for memristive systems:

- **Black Box (BB):** An adversary can only observe device inputs, outputs, and side-channel information such as power consumption or memory-access patterns.
- **White Box (WB):** The attacker has direct access to the internal structure and stored weights through interfaces such as M.2 or PCIe connections, or through invasive

techniques like micro-probing.

Both threat models are considered practically feasible in commercial memristive hardware platforms.

3. Memristors as Hardware Security Primitives

3.1 Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) & True Random Number Generators (TRNGs)

Memristors with their intrinsic stochastic behaviour and process variability have attracted attention for hardware security primitives. Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) utilise device-to-device (D2D) and cycle-to-cycle (C2C) variations arising from random conductive filament formation. The response characteristics of memristor-based PUFs are derived from write time, readout current, and resistance differences between cells. To counter modelling and cloning attacks, erasable and concealable PUF architectures have also been proposed [6]. Similarly, memristor-based TRNGs exploit the physical randomness of noise, voltage fluctuations, and readout current variations; memristor-based ring oscillators are commonly used for this purpose [11]. Chen et al. [9] highlighted a major limitation in existing TRNG research, stating that the noise sources of these TRNGs have not been understood intensively and often fail to satisfy strict cryptographic randomness requirements.

3.2 Analogue Cryptography Using Memristor Arrays

Cambou et al. [7] in their work proposed an analog cryptographic implementation using CBRAM memristor arrays. A message is divided into 4-bit blocks with modulated current applied to randomly selected cells; the resultant resistive states form a block cipher that can only be deciphered using the same physical array. The energy consumption of this implementation is governed by the power model:

$$P = \alpha \cdot \text{HW}(D) + \beta + N_{\text{el}} \quad (6)$$

where $\text{HW}(D)$ is the Hamming weight of the data word D , α is a proportionality constant relating switching activity to dynamic power, β is a static baseline, and N_{el} captures electrode noise contributions. This implementation reported low energy consumption of around 1 femtojoule per bit and claimed resistance against Differential Power Analysis (DPA), as the energy per bit is below the observable threshold. To improve session security, the authors employed a hash-based handshake protocol to generate cell addresses, access ordering, and driving currents. However, the authors acknowledged several limitations

including the lack of evaluation against frequency analysis, chosen-plaintext attacks, and man-in-the-middle attacks.

3.3 Cryptographic Logic Using Memristive Logic Families

Chen et al. [9] demonstrated cryptographic logic implementation using Complementary Resistive Switching with Reading (CRS-R) logic family based BiBFO memristors. These were capable of realising all 16 Boolean logic functions within three logic cycles: initialise, write, and read operations. Using this approach the authors implemented a 4-bit AES S-Box entirely from NOR gates, where each NOR gate is realised with a single BiBFO memristor. This work established a direct connection between memristor device physics and practical cryptographic circuit design.

4. Security Trade-offs in In-Memory Computing Architectures

4.1 NN Model Theft in Memristive Computing Systems

Zou et al. [6] classified countermeasures against memristor-based neural network model theft into five major categories. For the black-box scenario, one solution uses the obsolescence effect, where excess read operations gradually degrade memristor conductance and reduce accuracy for unauthorised users. Using superparamagnetic magnetic tunnel junction (s-MTJ) crossbars gives similar effects. Another defence uses Oblivious RAM (ORAM) techniques to obfuscate memory-access patterns and conceal neural-network structures from side-channel observation.

For the white-box scenario, encryption-based approaches apply full or partial XOR encryption to network weights before mapping them onto crossbar arrays. Partial encryption selectively protects sensitive layers and weights, reducing overhead. While encryption of model weights helps secure the entire model, it increases read/write operations on memristors, which leads to faster device failure, increased latency, and energy consumption. Moreover, decrypted weights are exposed during computation and can be exploited via power side-channel attacks.

An alternative WB countermeasure includes weight transformation techniques such as key-controlled MUX/DEMUX permutations, SRAM-based row and column remapping, and XOR-based encoding. Unlike encryption methods, these maintain continuous protection without requiring extra write operations. However, many are limited to binary or digital memristive systems and are not directly compatible with analog devices. Another method embeds hardware fingerprints (e.g., ADC offset characteristics) into the NN training process so that weights extracted from the device become useless on a different hardware platform. The authors concluded that no single defence mechanism addresses all security

requirements across both black-box and white-box threat models [6].

4.2 Processing-in-Memory (PIM) Architecture Trade-offs

Chi et al. [5] introduced a new PIM architecture for better neural-network computation built upon ReRAM crossbar arrays called PRIME. In PRIME sub-arrays can be utilized as either memory or as neural network accelerators. This can be achieved through modifying peripheral circuits including DACs, ADCs and column multiplexers. These features have previously unexplored attack surfaces by exposing additional peripheral interfaces that might leak any side channel information to the attacker. The dot-product operation underlying NN inference maps directly onto the crossbar VMM in Eq. (5), and current summation from Eq. (3) means that leakage currents from HRS cells accumulate across all m rows, creating an observable power signature. PRIME architecture also implemented inter-layer parallelism which allows partial outputs to be transferred directly among processing elements without repeated memory access. This will reduce leakage through memory access patterns but it does not eliminate power based side channel attacks. The authors did not provide an explicit security analysis of PRIME architecture; these security risks are based on the threat models discussed in Zou et al. [6].

5. Reliability and Attack Surface Analysis

5.1 Side-Channel Attacks on Memristive Logic-In-Memory (LIM)

Inglese et al. [8] reported side-channel attacks on MAGIC-based LIM architectures. They focused on the MAGIC-XOR operation due to its cryptographic relevance. MAGIC is more reliable for both cycle-to-cycle (C2C) and device-to-device (D2D) variations compared to FELIX and IMPLY-based architectures, but it exhibits a data-dependent power consumption profile that is inherently vulnerable to side-channel attacks. The large $R_{\text{off}}/R_{\text{on}}$ ratio in Eq. (4) means that LRS and HRS currents (Eq. (3)) differ by orders of magnitude, producing milliamp-to-microamp current differences that are trivial to exploit in differential power analysis. Simulation-based analysis revealed almost $3\times$ greater amplitude spikes in MAGIC-based XOR logic than in a conventional CMOS architecture for bit changes. The authors also demonstrated successful fault injection attacks.

5.2 Power-Balanced Hiding for Memristive Cryptographic Circuits

Chen et al. [9] proposed a hiding-based countermeasure for memristive cryptographic circuits by introducing *hiding groups*: gate types are combined such that power consumption—modelled by Eq. (6)—remains independent of the input data during read and write operations. All 16 Boolean gate types were organised into 2 or 3-cell hiding groups, with XOR and XNOR operations requiring more complex configurations. The method was

validated experimentally using a physical BiBFO memristor device. To assess leakage, the non-specific t -test statistic between two sets of power traces S_1 and S_2 was used:

$$t = \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} \quad (7)$$

where μ_k , s_k^2 , and n_k are the sample mean, variance, and size of trace set $k \in \{1, 2\}$. At 10% and 30% C2C variability levels the protected implementation passed t -test evaluations (Eq. (7)). However, the authors note that the t -test alone is insufficient to certify side-channel security, as it does not characterise the exploitability of the leakage. The implementation also incurred significant hardware overhead, increasing the memristor count by almost $3\times$ for NOR-gate-based designs. Inglese et al. [8] further argued that hiding countermeasures designed for CMOS systems may not be effective in memristive LIM architectures without dedicated security reassessment.

5.3 Side-Channel Attacks on Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs)

Nagarajan et al. [10] introduced a side-channel attack methodology targeting memristor-based spiking neural networks (SNNs) through the SCANN framework. This framework is aimed at extracting information such as synaptic weights, neuron counts per layer, membrane threshold voltages, and capacitor sizes. These attacks are evaluated in HSPICE simulations on a two-layer 3×3 SNN implemented using 65 nm PTM technology. The time-to-spike increases with synaptic resistance, which enables adversaries to deduce synaptic weights by monitoring spike timing through the power supply line. Other architectural parameters were also shown to leak through power characteristics. This study considered real threat actors including malicious insiders in cloud infrastructures, compromised power monitoring systems, and security researchers performing hardware evaluations. The authors argued that template-based attacks using foundry-calibrated simulations or a reference test chip could compensate for the effects of uncertainty introduced by process variation. The work is limited to simulation-based validation with no experimental demonstration on fabricated SNN hardware.

5.4 Fault Injection Attacks on Memristive LIM

Inglese et al. [8] investigated fault injection attacks on MAGIC-based logic-in-memory architectures using voltage glitching as the attack vector. They analysed three attack scenarios: (i) glitching the V_{set} signal alone, (ii) glitching the control voltage V_o alone, and (iii) glitching both parameters simultaneously. When V_{set} is glitched below the switching voltage threshold, the memristor output state becomes dependent on its unknown initial condition, leading to unpredictable behaviour. Lowering V_o caused the NOR operation to

fail silently. The authors showed that glitching V_o during any step of the MAGIC-XOR operation consistently corrupted the output, whereas glitches on V_{set} alone did not always produce exploitable faults. Simultaneous glitches across multiple cycles further reduced output predictability and increased fault injection effectiveness. Both voltage glitching and electromagnetic injection were considered by the authors.

6. Comparative Discussion Across Papers

The common insight across the reviewed works is that the non-volatility of memristors provides both security advantages and security risks. Non-volatility enables efficient storage and persistent hardware fingerprints for PUF applications, but opens a pathway to white-box attacks because neural-network weights and cryptographic states remain accessible without an active power supply. An adversary capable of micro-probing can therefore reconstruct sensitive models.

Several reviewed works also highlight that most protection methods—including SRAM-based permutations and XOR encoding—are applicable only to digital encoding devices and not to analog devices. Although analog memristive systems offer greater computational efficiency (as captured in the crossbar VMM of Eq. (5)), they expose resistance information that is prone to producing side-channel leakages. This issue is particularly evident in MAGIC-based logic systems, where the LRS-to-HRS current ratio (Eq. (4)) is orders of magnitude larger than the equivalent CMOS implementation.

In PUF architectures, device-to-device variability is the primary entropy source, while hiding countermeasures rely on cycle-to-cycle variability to raise the noise floor. Chen et al. [9] demonstrated that their hiding strategy remained effective under 30% C2C variability, as quantified by the t -statistic in Eq. (7). Shivaram et al. [3] noted that variability in TiO_2 -based memristors strongly depends on fabrication factors such as synthesis methods, electrode materials, and doping conditions, indicating process-dependent security properties.

Another major concern is that many security measures consume memristor endurance. Techniques like encryption and re-keying introduce additional write operations on memristors, which have limited endurance (typically 10^{10} to 10^{12} cycles); security overheads can therefore reduce the operational lifetime of memristive systems. This trade-off between security features and device lifetime needs to be explicitly addressed in future work.

7. Research Gaps & Open Challenges

The current research on memristive security systems remains scattered; most proposed countermeasures address only a single class of attack. There is no proposed defence

framework that simultaneously mitigates side-channel, fault, learning, and white-box extraction attacks without increasing hardware, energy, and endurance overheads. Side-channel analysis of memristive architectures remains far less mature than for conventional CMOS, FPGA, or ASIC-based cryptographic systems.

A major limitation across the reviewed literature is the lack of experimental validation on fabricated hardware. Side-channel vulnerabilities and fault analyses have been demonstrated only in simulation, and no fully fabricated memristive cryptographic system has been examined under practical differential power or electromagnetic attacks. Similarly, many CMOS-derived countermeasures have not been validated for alternative memristive logic families such as MAGIC-based LIM.

Unresolved challenges also persist in memristive neural network security. Countermeasures based on the obsolescence effect or stochastic switching target unauthorised users, while authorised adversaries with unrestricted query access may still reconstruct models. Architectures like PRIME have been evaluated for performance and energy efficiency but lack security analysis. Analog memristor-based encryption schemes have significant uncertainty around cryptographic robustness, as many proposed systems have not been evaluated against frequency analysis, chosen-plaintext attacks, or chosen-ciphertext attacks.

8. Conclusion

The reviewed literature shows that the attractive features of memristors for in-memory computing also create fundamentally different security problems and trade-offs compared to CMOS systems. Non-volatility enables white-box attacks, allowing adversaries to access weights and internal states without powering the device. The large $R_{\text{off}}/R_{\text{on}}$ ratio (Eq. (4)) amplifies power side-channel leakage, producing mA-to- μ A current swings (Eq. (3)) that are easily observed in differential power analysis. At the same time, device variability acts as a security advantage by serving as an entropy source for PUFs, yet it complicates the design of reliable hiding-based countermeasures quantified via the t -test in Eq. (7).

Memristors also face endurance–security trade-offs: countermeasures requiring additional write operations directly reduce operational lifetime. Countermeasures such as weight transformation, partial encryption, fingerprint embedding, and power-balanced hiding address specific attack dimensions. One significant unresolved problem remains: the design of a security framework for memristor-based hardware capable of protecting against multiple—ideally all—attack surfaces simultaneously.

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